

Abstract

I chose this project to learn more about optics and understand how different liquids changed the way light behaved. This study not only helped me learn more about physics but also gave me practical insights into everyday things, like why objects looked bent in water. It also helped me build my experimental skills and gain a better appreciation for scientific research.

Introduction

The study of refractive indices is essential for understanding how light interacts with various substances. This project aims to determine the refractive indices of glycerin, oil, and acetone using a convex lens and other optical apparatus.

Materials

The materials used in this experiment are:
a convex lens, plane mirror, optical needle, spherometer, and the liquids; glycerin, oil, and acetone.

Explanation

The refractive index of a medium is a measure of how much light bends when it enters the medium from another medium. It is defined as the ratio of the speed of light in a vacuum to the speed of light in the medium. Mathematically, it is expressed as:

$$\mu = \frac{c}{v}$$

where (μ) is the refractive index, (c) is the speed of light in a vacuum, and (v) is the speed of light in the medium. The refractive index indicates how much the light slows down and changes direction when passing through the medium.

In this experiment, the focal length of the convex lens is first measured in air. Then, the lens is combined with each liquid, and the new focal length is measured. Using the spherometer, the radius of curvature of the lens is determined. These measurements are used to calculate the refractive indices of the liquids by applying the lens maker's formula:

$$\frac{1}{f} = (\mu - 1) \left(\frac{1}{R_1} - \frac{1}{R_2} \right)$$

where (f) is the focal length, (μ) is the refractive index, and (R_1) and (R_2) are the radii of curvature of the lens surfaces.

Since the R_2 is ∞ , μ can be found out easily. The final equation to find the refractive

index (μ) is:

$$\mu = \frac{R}{f_2} + 1$$

Focal Length of the Convex Lens

The focal length of the convex lens is a critical parameter in this experiment. It is measured by focusing a distant object and determining the distance between the lens and the image formed. This value is then used in subsequent calculations to find the refractive indices of the liquids.

The rough focal length of the convex lens used is 21 cm.

The Radius of Curvature of the Convex Lens

The radius of curvature of the convex lens is needed to find the Refractive Index, using the lens maker formula. It is calculated using the for

$$R = \frac{l^2}{6h} + \frac{h}{2}$$

where (l) is the average distance between the legs of the spherometer, and (h) is the difference in the reading of the spherometer when placed on the convex lens and then on a plane mirror.

Analysis

(a) To find the Focal Length of the Convex Lens

1. Find the rough focal length of the convex lens.
2. Place a plane mirror on the horizontal base of the iron stand, and then place the convex lens on the plane mirror.
3. Hold the needle in the clamp stand and adjust its position on the stand such that there is no parallax between the tip of the needle and its image.
4. Measure the distance between the tip of the needle and the upper surface of the lens using a plumb line and a half-meter scale. Also, measure the distance between the tip of the needle and the upper surface of the mirror. Take the mean of the two readings. This mean distance will be equal to the focal length of the convex lens (f_1).

(b) To find the Focal length of the Combination

5. Put a few drops of water on the plane mirror and place the convex lens over it with the same face up as before. The water spreads into a thin layer and acts like a plano-concave lens.
6. Repeat steps 3 and 4 to determine the equivalent focal length of the combination.
7. Record the observations.
8. Repeat steps 5, 6, and 7 using other liquids; glycerin, oil, and acetone.

(c) For Radius of Curvature of Convex Lens (R)

9. Determine the pitch and the least count of the spherometer.
10. Remove the convex lens and dry it completely. Place the spherometer on the lens surface.
11. Ensure all three legs of the spherometer are placed symmetrically on the lens, and adjust the central screw tip to touch the surface of the lens.

12. Remove the spherometer from the lens surface and place it on the plane mirror surface. Record the reading.

13. Repeat steps 10 and 11 three times.

14. Obtain the impressions of the three legs of the spherometer on a paper, mark them, and measure their average distance using:

$$l = \frac{l_1 + l_2 + l_3}{3}$$

Observations

1) To find focal length 'f' of lens and combination

		Distance of needle tip from	Distance of needle tip from		
S.no	Arrangement	Tip of the upper surface of the convex lens (cm)	Upper surface of the plane mirror (cm)	Mean	Focal length (cm)
		x_1	x_2	$\frac{x_1 + x_2}{2}$	f
1	Without liquid	31	33	32	$F_1 = 32$
2	With glycerin	14.1	14.3	14.2	$F_g = 14.2$
3	With acetone	15.2	15.6	15.4	$F_a = 15.4$
4	With oil	16	16.1	16.05	$F_o = 16.05$

2) To find h

S.no	Initial reading of the C.S. on the convex lens	No of rotations by CS	Final CS reading on glass plate	Additional C.S divisions moved	$h = n \times \text{pitch} + m \times L.C$
	(a)	(n)	(b)	(m)	(cm)
1	10	1	80	30	0.13
2	20	1	90.5	29.5	0.129

Mean h = 0.13

Calculations

1) Mean distance between two legs

$$l = \frac{l_1 + l_2 + l_3}{3}$$

$$\rightarrow 3.5\text{cm}$$

2) To find the radius of curvature of the convex lens

$$R = \frac{l^2}{6h} + \frac{h}{2}$$

$$\rightarrow 15.7\text{cm}$$

3) Measurement of refractive indices of glycerin, oil and acetone

■ For Glycerin

$$\mu_1 = \frac{R}{f_g} + 1 = \frac{21}{43.85} + 1 = 1.47$$

■ For oil

$$\mu_2 = \frac{R}{f_o} + 1 = \frac{15.7}{23.24} + 1 = 1.67$$

■ For acetone

$$\mu_3 = \frac{R}{f_a} + 1 = \frac{21}{57.75} + 1 = 1.36$$

Precautions

- 1) Ensure the plane mirror is clean and fully reflective.
 - 2) Use only transparent liquids for accurate results.
 - 3) Remove parallax by aligning the needle tip precisely.
 - 4) Maintain a distance of about 30 cm from the needle while removing parallax.
 - 5) Use only a few drops of liquid to form a thin layer.
 - 6) Keep the legs of the spherometer vertical.
 - 7) Turn the central leg of the spherometer in one direction only.
-

Sources of Error

- 1) The liquid may not be completely transparent.
- 2) The parallax may not be entirely eliminated.
- 3) The spherometer legs should be placed symmetrically on the surface of the convex lens.
- 4) The tip of the central screw should not merely touch the surface of the lens or mirror.

Conclusion

In this project, I have learned how to determine the refractive indices of various liquids using a convex lens and other optical apparatus. By measuring the focal lengths and radii of curvature, I applied the lens maker's formula to calculate the refractive indices. This experiment has enhanced my understanding of how light interacts with different media and the principles behind optical instruments.

Results

The refractive index of glycerine is $(\mu_1) = 1.47$

The refractive index of oil is $(\mu_2) = 1.67$

The refractive index of acetone $(\mu_3) = 1.36$.

Bibliography

S.No	Website
1.	https://www.physicslab.com
2.	https://phys.libretexts.org/
3	NOOTAN Physics ISC Class XII Textbook (Part II)
3.	https://www.sciencedirect.com/